

Modular Generative AI Training to Promote AI Literacy Across the University

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Abstract

In the recent years Generative AI (GenAI) has been a subject of active discussions amongst both educators and students. While the use of AI is becoming more widespread, the levels of AI literacy across the university differ. These inequalities need to be addressed, because effective use of GenAI is rapidly becoming an important academic and professional skill – something that should not be ignored. Additionally, both faculty and students need clarity on how the use of GenAI aligns with academic integrity requirements.

Many universities and businesses have designed various courses and trainings on GenAI, navigating through which is challenging. Moreover, there is no “one-size fits all” solution here. Therefore, we have developed modular GenAI workshops that can be customised to address the needs of students and staff from different faculties. These workshops were delivered to Swansea University staff and students by the team from the Institute of Coding in Wales and Computer Science Department, in collaboration with NAIADES (Network for Artificial Intelligence, the Arts, the Digital Economy and Society).

The workshops consist of the four core parts: subject-specific context, history and ethics of GenAI, technical aspects of GenAI and prompt engineering, and the education-related issues of GenAI. These parts can be mixed and matched to address specific audiences and their needs.

The aim of this session is to share our experience designing and delivering these customisable GenAI workshops and discuss their impact on AI literacy. We also aim to inspire our colleagues to collaborate with us in expanding these workshops to suit their particular subject areas, and through this to improve AI literacy and adherence to academic integrity requirements across the university.

The session will cover two sub-themes:

- The ethics of using GenAI (academic integrity, sustainability)

- The development of academic skills to leverage GenAI technology effectively.

Attendees will gain a deeper understanding of the ethical considerations surrounding the use of GenAI in academic settings, as well as practical strategies for integrating this technology into their teaching practice and research in a responsible and effective manner.